

OCEANIS

Collaborative Planning for Integrated Ocean Action

A workshop quick start guiding tool to encourage cross-domain thinking
and develop action plans

How to run a workshop: A step-by-step guide

Planning a Workshop

OCEANIS is a **collaborative, non-prescriptive planning tool** for integrated ocean action, providing support to facilitate structured workshops.

OCEANIS workshops are suggested for groups of 2-8 people, but can also be done solo or in larger groups. Due to the transdisciplinary nature of this workshop, it can accommodate participants with different types of expertise. As a facilitator, please familiarise yourself with this guide before you begin.

To run a workshop you will need:

- A copy of the step-by-step guide for each person,
- The OCEANIS Spiderweb printed in A3 or equivalent (page 9),
- Extra paper to take notes, pens, and highlighters (of different colours) for each person,
- Computer for online resources (optional),
- A meeting room (in person or virtual),
- Active participation

Workshops begin with an introduction, followed by **four interactive rounds**. We recommend setting aside **2-3 hours** to run a workshop, . see next page for an overview of suggested times for each round.

Online Resources

We have developed several online resources to support OCEANIS workshops. Scan the QR code or visit the link to our online supportive resources, including:

- An **introductory video** from the authors
- A supplementary PowerPoint to use during the workshop
- An online **interactive version** of OCEANIS
- Links to associated **resources**
- Further background on OCEANIS

<https://bioecocean.org/oceanis>

OCEANIS Development

OCEANIS was developed through a 3-year co-creative process, with contributions from hundreds of individuals to ensure it is user-friendly, inclusive and fit-for-purpose. The BioEcoOcean consortium, funded by the European Union, has contributed significantly to the development of this tool.

Main creators of this guide:

Elizabeth Lawrence, UNESCO IOC Project Office IODE, OBIS
Lina Mtwana Nordlund, Uppsala University, Sweden

To be cited as:

Lawrence, E.R., Nordlund, L.M. (2026). OCEANIS Quick Start guide: A Collaborative Planning tool for Integrated Ocean Action. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18672397>

Welcome & Introduction

~15 min

Welcome to the OCEANIS Workshop!

INSTRUCTIONS

To begin, ensure everyone has a copy of this step-by-step guide. Welcome everyone to the workshop. If you don't know each other, introduce yourselves!

Start the workshop by introducing OCEANIS. This can be done by watching the introductory video and/or reading the information about OCEANIS on the next page. Then the workshop proceeds in four rounds of discussions, summarised to the right. The timings of each round are suggestions. The workshop aims to encourage a more holistic and integrated approach to your work. This process may take time and might need to be tackled in many steps, and in multiple workshops.

Access the introductory video through the QR code or by visiting <https://bioecocean.org/oceanis>.

Intro

Gather your group, introduce yourselves and OCEANIS

~15 min

Round 1

Define your main goal and motivation, determine the geographic and temporal context

~15 min

Round 2

Familiarise yourself with the OCEANIS Spiderweb, select a broad or specific approach

Discuss the components

~60 min

Round 3

Select components of importance. Discuss the connections between them and how they can be strengthened

~40 min

Round 4

Summarise your findings and identify the next steps

~20 min

What is OCEANIS?

Introduction

What is OCEANIS? It is a **guiding tool** facilitating workshops based around questions to **reflect and plan** all aspects of a project, program, proposal, or other initiative. It can be used at any project stage, and we encourage coming back to it regularly. OCEANIS is visualised by a **Spiderweb** with interconnected components. Each component consists of descriptors, themes, and associated question words, as well as questions connecting the components.

OCEANIS is intentionally non-directive, and brings key issues and perspectives to be explored and addressed, rather than prescribe solutions or dictate decisions.

You may already be thinking about some of the aspects presented in OCEANIS - which is great! We encourage thinking beyond individual questions to explore **connections** between the OCEANIS components and support **holistic thinking**.

For whom? OCEANIS is designed with ocean observing systems in mind, but it can also be applied for more general use and at **any career stage**. It is especially useful for those who want to collaborate and think more holistically.

Why is this tool beneficial? OCEANIS supports workshop participants move beyond siloed thinking by providing a structured pathway to explore cross-domain solutions. It creates an intentional space to connect perspectives, broaden understanding, and collaboratively develop action plans. OCEANIS also provides relevant online resources to support planning.

OCEANIS Components

OCEANIS has **eight interconnected components** that consider themes across all stages of a project, such as communication and outreach, data collection, and evaluation. The components are visualised as a Spiderweb. There is **one blank space** in the Spiderweb, this allows you to include any other aspects you find relevant.

Often, we might think about each of these components individually or linearly, and forget about the interconnectedness. OCEANIS aims to support us in strengthening these important connections.

Round 1: What is the overarching objective?

🕒 ~15 min

INSTRUCTIONS

As a group, define your **overarching objective(s)** to address during the workshop. What is the context and/or goal? Are you scoping, designing, implementing, or evaluating? This could alternatively be defined by the workshop facilitator ahead of time and then discussed as a group. During this round, formulate the overarching objective as detailed as possible in your own words below, and define the **geographical and temporal context**, if relevant. Note that you can come back to this page at any time to further refine the goal. You may also want to include any **personal notes** that are related to the overarching objective.

Overarching Objective(s)

Personal Notes

Examples of broad objectives may include:

- Project planning (project around the island for the coming 2 years)
- Filling a need in society (Community x, in y time frame)
- Identify gaps in our workflow (open ocean, last 4 years)
- Evaluate your current system or project (regional, 2 years)
- Gain a more holistic overview / integrated ocean observing system (shallow habitats, last monitoring season)
- Strengthen communication among stakeholders, sectors and components (global/local, no time frame)
- Design a lab-based experiment (controlled environment, 4 months)
- Improve data modelling pipelines (no specific geography, 1 year)

Geographical Context

Temporal Context

Round 2a: Familiarise with OCEANIS

🕒 ~15 min

INSTRUCTIONS

Take a few minutes to look at the Spiderweb to the right, the heart of OCEANIS. Starting from the innermost layer are the **components**. Each component has **descriptor words** further describing the component. The **themes** provide context and should be combined with the **question words** below.

Question Words:

WHO
WHAT
WHEN
WHERE
WHY
HOW

Review the **components** and associated **descriptor words** and **themes**. With your overarching objective in mind, highlight or circle the components of interest on the Spiderweb. You may select components where you want to improve, or have limited knowledge or awareness. Feel free to write your own component in the blank space.

Round 2b: Choose an Approach & Discuss

~60 min

INSTRUCTIONS

Now that you have individually identified interesting components, it is time to decide on the group's approach for the rest of the workshop. Choose if you want to select only a few components to discuss, or take an overall picture (i.e. all components, which may have to be done over multiple workshops).

Overall Picture

Focused Session

After selecting an approach, decide which component to start with and choose how much time you want to spend on it. Think about the question words, the what, who, when etc., in combination with descriptors and themes. With your overarching objective in mind, **create relevant questions** that you would like to explore. Two examples of how to create questions are provided below:

Example 1: Component: *Exploration*, Descriptor: *Map*, Theme: *Knowledge landscape*. Question word: *How*. Create the question: *How do we map out the knowledge landscape?*

Example 2: Component: *Data Management*, Theme: *Metadata and traceability*. Create the Question: *What is metadata and traceability, and what is needed to make it? Who will be in charge of documenting our metadata? Who has the knowledge to do this?*

The questions you are formulating do not need to be answered in this workshop, but if relevant, added to your action plan. Write relevant questions in the box to the right. Then move to the next component.

Questions

Round 3: Connecting the Components

🕒 ~40 min

INSTRUCTIONS

In this round, we go beyond the individual components and **focus on how they connect**. Based on the components discussed in the former round, highlight the connections between components that *you* want to explore, build, or strengthen on the Spiderweb to the right. For example, you could highlight the links between *Data Collection* and *Societal Relevance*, or among *Data Management*, *Data Products* and *Communication & Outreach*.

Then, as a group, decide which connections to focus on in your discussion with respect to your overarching objective.

You may use these guiding questions for your discussion:

- How do these components connect?
- What connections need to be developed?
- What hinders or helps the connection between these components?
- What is missing to make these connections work more smoothly in practice?
- How could we overcome challenges?

Record key points from the discussion that you want to bring forward to your action plan, including ideas of how these connections could be addressed or strengthened.

Notes

Round 4a: Summarise Your Findings

🕒 ~20 min

INSTRUCTIONS

Summarise your key findings from the first 3 rounds of the workshop in the box to the right. Use the Status markings below to indicate which components have been addressed, not addressed, partially addressed, or require more discussion. This will help plan future workshops and create your action plan.

Status

- Addressed
- Not addressed
- Partially Addressed
- Not applicable
- Requires further discussion

You may also use the following guiding questions:

- What insights have you gained regarding your objectives?
- What are the new things you have learned?
- Which components require further investigation or consideration?
- Which connections are already strong?
- Which connections are most urgent to address?

Key Findings

Large empty box for recording key findings.

Round 4b: Next Steps

🕒 ~20 min

INSTRUCTIONS

To close your OCEANIS workshop, identify the **next steps** you and your team can take. Use the space to the right to write down short- and long-term steps to form your **action plan**. Be sure to include any OCEANIS components and connections that need to be addressed. You might also want to identify who is doing what.

Consider keeping copies of the OCEANIS notes for reference for the next workshop. Explore the online OCEANIS resources for tools or information to support your action plan.

Finally, close the session by acknowledging that this is a process that can be returned to at any point. Congratulations on completing the OCEANIS workshop!

Short Term

Long Term

OCEANIS Spiderweb

What?

Who?

Where?

Why?

When?

How?

Thanks for participating!
Best wishes from the BioEcoOcean team

Funded by the European Union project BioEcoOcean, Grant No. 101136748. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.